

IMPORTANCE OF INDUSTRIAL ZONES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the reforms carried out in connection with the organization of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country and its effective management and development, the establishment of small industrial zones in the regions, and through this, providing employment to the unemployed population living in rural areas, as well as the issues of increasing the population's income, are highlighted.

Introduction. Great attention is paid to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Development Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" and Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 No. PQ-4611 International Financial Reporting The adoption of the Decision "On additional measures for the transition to the standards" allows for a systematic solution to the issues of establishing business entities in the regions and effectively conducting their activities. It was emphasized that the main focus today is the development of small businesses and entrepreneurship in rural areas, their comprehensive support, the importance of identifying and helping young people who are trying to start and develop their own entrepreneurship.

By performing the above tasks, an opportunity will be created to increase the number of business entities and thereby create additional jobs. In this regard, in order to reduce poverty in our country, special attention is paid to solving the problems of providing employment to the population and at the same time to the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Material and methods. It is necessary to use the most effective research methods to find solutions to the problems that await their solution in the field.

In particular, methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparative analysis, questionnaire survey, expert evaluation of results, economic analysis and economic-statistical methods are effective in conducting research.

Analyzes and results.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" stipulates the creation of favorable conditions for each business entity based on the characteristics of their activity. .

As Uzbekistan bases its development on the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is the most urgent, it relies on the achievements of the advanced countries of the world in this regard. At the same time, he puts his model into practice.

The adoption of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 No. PQ-4611 "On additional measures for the transition to international standards of financial reporting" made financial statements comprehensible to foreign investors is speeding up the process of compiling financial reports based on the requirements of international standards.

As part of the implementation of the Development Strategy for 2022-2026 in Uzbekistan, it is planned to halve the level of the low-income population in the country by the end of 2026. The task of ensuring macroeconomic stability and stable economic growth at a high rate is set as the main conditions for achieving the set goals. It was noted that ensuring the implementation of such tasks will create a foundation for Uzbekistan to enter the upper group of middle-income countries by 2030.

Implementation of these tasks takes time, and in this regard, the government of our country has developed separate strategic programs in various directions.

In our opinion, by establishing small industrial zones in rural areas, it is possible to solve the following issues:

- the infrastructure of residential areas will be further improved;
- provides an opportunity to widely involve the population of the region in entrepreneurship;
- local residents living in the regions will be provided with additional work.

Increasing the number of small industrial areas to be established, creating a favorable business environment for entrepreneurs, developing and implementing additional measures in this regard will create the basis for the further development of industry in rural areas in the future, due to this, not only production, but also services areas will also be widely developed. Some problems are also being solved by gradually reducing tax rates in order to further encourage the effective activity of entrepreneurs and the formation of working capital.

In practice, business income tax rates are being reduced. This, in turn, creates an opportunity for more income at the expense of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs have the opportunity to use such funds to expand production and solve other issues.

Organization of small industrial zones also aims to unite entrepreneurs. While implementing such large projects in rural areas, it is an important issue to organize its control. For this, it is advisable to organize the following activities:

- Continuous monitoring of activities in the small industrial zone;
- Organization of various exhibitions to help find a buyer for the products produced in the industrial area;
- Organization of continuous improvement of the skills of entrepreneurs operating in the small industrial zone.

It is necessary to take systematic measures that cannot be delayed to solve the problems that have arisen in the development of entrepreneurship in industrial zones.

Conclusion. We should effectively use the opportunities provided by our state to develop entrepreneurship in our republic. Eliminating existing problems will serve to create large production and service enterprises in rural areas and increase the number of business entities in the future. The purpose of this is to create jobs and provide employment to the unemployed population, to further improve the standard of living of the population, and to achieve an increase in the income of entrepreneurs.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Development Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". 2021 year.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 No. PQ-4611 "On additional measures for the transition to international standards of financial reporting". Tashkent. 2020 year.
3. Aripov O.A. State regulation of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. - T.: Science, 2012. - 272 p.
4. Aripov O.A. Development of small business and private enterprise and creation of business environment. // "Economy and innovation technologies" magazine. No. 2, March-April, 2019.
5. Mustafaqulov Sh., Murodullaev N., Hamidov R., Rahimberdiyev O. Identifying and reducing poverty in Uzbekistan at the level of state policy. // Economy and innovative technologies. (1(2), 68-85.
6. Sobirov O. O., Odilov H. M. Costs Included in Product Production and Factors Affecting Them //AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 07.
7. Собиров О. О. Бошқарув ҳисобининг моҳияти ва уни ташкил этишда харажатларнинг ўрни //Scientific Journal of "International Finance& Accounting".-Т.: ТМИ. – 2022.
8. Собиров О. О. Бошқарув ҳисобининг моҳияти ва уни ташкил этишда харажатларнинг ўрни //Scientific Journal of "International Finance& Accounting".-Т.: ТМИ. – 2022.
9. Sobirov O. O. Product Development Cost Factors Affecting Reduction //AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 07.
10. Собиров О. Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорликда бухгалтерия ҳисоби ва ҳисоботларини халқаро стандартлар асосида такомиллаштириш //Монография. Наманган. – 2022.
11. Собиров О. Хўжалик юритувчи субъектларда бошқарув ҳисобини самарали юритишни такомиллаштириш //Архив научных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
12. Sobirov O. O. Improment of management accounting methodology in economic entities //Scientific Journal of "International Finance & Accounting" ТМИ. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 2181-1016.
13. Sobirov O. O. Improvement of management accounting in economic entities //Abstract of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation on Economic Sciences. Tashkent. ТМИ. – 2022.
14. Sobirov O. Boshqaruv hisobida mas' uliyat markazlarini tashkil etish masalalari. – 2024.
15. Otabek S., Javahir H. Analysis of Factors Affecting the Financial Stability of Small Business Subjects //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 892-895.
16. Otabek S., Khamidillo O. The Importance of Organizing Industrial Zones in the Development of Small Business //Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521). – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 1011-1113.

17. Sobirov O. BOSHQARUV HISOBI METODOLOGIYASINI ZAMONAVIY TIZIMLAR ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2024. – T. 25. – №. 2. – C. 60-64.
18. Sobirov O.O. O'zbekiston Respublikasida auditorlik faoliyatini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish. "Innovatsion yondashuv asosida moliyaviy xisobotning xalqaro standartlarini joriy etish" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to'plami.Toshkent, TMI.2022 yil 16 sentabr.
19. Sobirov O.O. Xo'jalik yurituvchi sub'ektlarda boshqaruv hisobini takmillashtirish yo'nalishlari.i.f.f.d.(PhD) ishi avtoreferati.T: TMI. 2022 yil.
20. Собиров О. Молиявий ҳисоботларни халқаро стандартлар талаблари даражасида такомиллаштириш.« //Халқаро молия ва ҳисоб» илмий журнали. – 2021. – Т. 3. – С. 2181-1016.
21. Olimjonovich S. O. The Cost Of Forming A Management Account In Business Entities //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2022. – C. 4295-4298.
22. Sobirov O. Improvement of financial reports to the level of international standards." //International Finance and Accounting" scientific journal. – 2021. – T.

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